

Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Orders - III

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Abstract

We know that we can always write **block-wise magic squares** of any order except for the orders of type p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. On the other hand we can always write **bordered magic squares** of any order. The aims of this work is to combine the both, i.e., **bordered** and **block-wise** magic squares, for the magic squares of **prime** and **double prime** orders. We call it as **block-bordered** magic squares. The magic squares considered in this work are of orders 41, 43, 46, 47 and 51. In order to bring these **block-bordered** magic squares, we make use of author's previous works on **block-wise** constructions of magic squares [35, 38]. This is the third part of the work. The first and second part [54, 55] works with orders, 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 19, 22, 26, 29, 31, 34, 37 and 38. The forth part of the work shall be on magic squares of orders 58, 59 and 61.

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1 Basic Magic Squares

Below are some magic squares well known in the literature. These are of orders, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. In some cases, these magic squares are **pandiagonal** and or **bimagic**. These are generally used for the constructions of **block-wise magic squares** given in Section 3 as Appendix or refer as Appendix 3.

1.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 1.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 3 is given by*

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $3k$, $k > 2$.

1.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Example 1.2. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 4.*

		34	34	34	34
	7	12	1	14	34
34	2	13	8	11	34
34	16	3	10	5	34
34	9	6	15	4	34
	34	34	34	34	34

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $4k$, $k > 1$

1.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 1.3. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 5 is given by*

		65	65	65	65	65
	1	9	12	20	23	65
65	17	25	3	6	14	65
65	8	11	19	22	5	65
65	24	2	10	13	16	65
65	15	18	21	4	7	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $5k$, $k > 2$

1.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 1.4. *Let's consider a magic square of order 6.*

						111
1	35	34	33	2	6	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $6k$, $k > 1$

1.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 1.5. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 7 is given by*

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175	
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175	
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175	
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175	
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175	
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175	
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175	
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $7k$, $k > 2$

1.6 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 8

Example 1.6. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 8 is given by*

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	25	48	1	56	26	47	2	55	260
260	8	49	32	41	7	50	31	42	260
260	64	9	40	17	63	10	39	18	260
260	33	24	57	16	34	23	58	15	260
260	27	46	3	54	28	45	4	53	260
260	6	51	30	43	5	52	29	44	260
260	62	11	38	19	61	12	37	20	260
260	35	22	59	14	36	21	60	13	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $8k$, $k > 1$

Example 1.7. *Let's consider a pandiagonal bimagic square of order 8 given by*

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	16	41	36	5	27	62	55	18	260	
260	26	63	54	19	13	44	33	8	260	
260	1	40	45	12	22	51	58	31	260	
260	23	50	59	30	4	37	48	9	260	
260	38	3	10	47	49	24	29	60	260	
260	52	21	32	57	39	2	11	46	260	
260	43	14	7	34	64	25	20	53	260	
260	61	28	17	56	42	15	6	35	260	
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

In this case, each 2×4 blocks entries sum is same as of magic square, i.e., 260.

1.7 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 9

Example 1.8. Let's consider a *pandiagonal magic square of order 9* is given by

		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
	8	49	66	61	24	38	36	77	10	369
369	37	63	23	12	35	76	65	7	51	369
369	78	11	34	50	64	9	22	39	62	369
369	14	28	81	67	3	53	42	56	25	369
369	52	69	2	27	41	55	80	13	30	369
369	57	26	40	29	79	15	1	54	68	369
369	20	43	60	73	18	32	48	71	4	369
369	31	75	17	6	47	70	59	19	45	369
369	72	5	46	44	58	21	16	33	74	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Additionally, it has the property that blocks of order 3 are of equal sum as of magic square, i.e., $S_9 = 369$. Moreover, each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square** (only in rows and columns).

Example 1.9. Let's consider a *bimagic square of order 9* given by

									369
1	18	23	35	40	48	60	65	79	369
33	38	52	55	72	77	8	13	21	369
62	67	75	6	11	25	28	45	50	369
27	5	10	49	30	44	74	61	69	369
47	34	42	81	59	64	22	3	17	369
76	57	71	20	7	15	54	32	37	369
14	19	9	39	53	31	70	78	56	369
43	51	29	68	73	63	12	26	4	369
66	80	58	16	24	2	41	46	36	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Blocks of order 3 are of equal sum entries as of magic square, i.e., 369. The **bimagic** sum is $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 20049$.

The **bimagic squares** of orders 8 and 9 given in examples 1.7 and 1.9 are the classical **bimagic squares** constructed for the first time by G. Pfeffermann [9] in 1819.

The aims of this work is to write **block-bordered** magic squares of orders 41, 43, 46, 47 and 53. In order to bring these **block-bordered** magic squares, we make use of author's previous works on **block-wise** constructions of magic squares and online program by H. White [10, 11] for **bordered** magic squares. The **bordered** magic squares considered are of orders 41, 43, 46, 47 and 53. The **block-wise** magic square used are of orders 39, 40, 42, 44, 45, 49 and 51. Some idea on bordered magic squares can also be seen in [4, 13]. Some study on **bordered** magic square can be seen in author's work [41, 42, 43, 44, 45].

2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares

The subsection below give block-bordered magic squares of orders, 41, 43, 47 and 51. For the construction of these magic squares we used the block-wise magic squares of orders 39, 40, 42, 44, 45, 49 and 51. These block-wise magic squares are given Section 3 as Appendix.

2.1 Bordered Magic Squares of Order 41

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 41 given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{781, 782, \dots, 799, 800, D_{9 \times 9}, 882, 883, \dots, 900, 901\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 9251; \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{757, 758, \dots, 779, 780, D_{11 \times 11}, 902, 903, \dots, 924, 925\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 10933; \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{729, 730, \dots, 755, 756, D_{13 \times 13}, 926, 927, \dots, 952, 953\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 12615; \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{697, 698, \dots, 727, 728, D_{15 \times 15}, 954, 955, \dots, 984, 985\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 14297; \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{661, 662, \dots, 695, 696, D_{17 \times 17}, 986, 987, \dots, 1020, 1021\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 15979; \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{621, 622, \dots, 659, 660, D_{19 \times 19}, 1022, 1023, \dots, 1060, 1061\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 17661; \\
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{577, 578, \dots, 619, 620, D_{21 \times 21}, 1062, 1063, \dots, 1104, 1105\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 19343; \\
 D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{529, 530, \dots, 575, 576, D_{23 \times 23}, 1106, 1107, \dots, 1152, 1153\}; & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 21025; \\
 D_{27 \times 27} &:= \{477, 478, \dots, 527, 528, D_{25 \times 25}, 1154, 1155, \dots, 1204, 1205\}; & S_{27 \times 27} &:= 22707; \\
 D_{29 \times 29} &:= \{421, 422, \dots, 475, 476, D_{27 \times 27}, 1206, 1207, \dots, 1260, 1261\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 24389; \\
 D_{31 \times 31} &:= \{361, 518, \dots, 419, 420, D_{29 \times 29}, 1262, 1263, \dots, 1320, 1321\}; & S_{31 \times 31} &:= 26071; \\
 D_{33 \times 33} &:= \{297, 298, \dots, 359, 360, D_{31 \times 31}, 1322, 1323, \dots, 1384, 1385\}; & S_{33 \times 33} &:= 27753; \\
 D_{35 \times 35} &:= \{229, 230, \dots, 215, 296, D_{33 \times 33}, 1386, 1387, \dots, 1452, 1453\}; & S_{35 \times 35} &:= 29435; \\
 D_{37 \times 37} &:= \{157, 158, \dots, 227, 228, D_{35 \times 35}, 1454, 2155, \dots, 1424, 1525\}; & S_{37 \times 37} &:= 31117; \\
 D_{39 \times 39} &:= \{81, 82, \dots, 155, 156, D_{37 \times 37}, 1526, 1527, \dots, 1600, 1601\}; & S_{39 \times 39} &:= 32799; \\
 D_{41 \times 41} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 79, 80, D_{39 \times 39}, 1602, 1603, \dots, 1680, 1681\}; & S_{41 \times 41} &:= 34481.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 41. These are based on the magic squares of order 39 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.1 and 3.2.

2.1.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1521 by 81 to 1601 in Example 3.1 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{39 \times 39}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 41 given by

$$S_{41 \times 41} := 34481, \quad S_{39 \times 39} := 32799 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{13 \times 13} := 10933.$$

Blocks of order 13 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**.

Result 2.1. *We have written a **block-bordered** magic square of order 41 in two different ways, where the **block-wise magic squares** considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 39, where each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square** with equal semi-magic sums;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 39, where each block of order 13 is a **pandiagonal magic square** with equal magic sums.*

2.2 Bordered Magic Squares of Order 43

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a **bordered magic square** of order 43 given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{885, 886, \dots, 899, 900, D_{7 \times 7}, 950, 951, \dots, 964, 965\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 8325; \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{865, 866, \dots, 883, 884, D_{9 \times 9}, 966, 967, \dots, 984, 985\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 10175; \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{841, 842, \dots, 863, 864, D_{11 \times 11}, 986, 987, \dots, 1008, 1009\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 12025; \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{813, 814, \dots, 839, 840, D_{13 \times 13}, 1010, 1011, \dots, 1036, 1037\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 13875; \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{781, 782, \dots, 811, 812, D_{15 \times 15}, 1038, 1039, \dots, 1068, 1069\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 15725; \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{745, 746, \dots, 779, 780, D_{17 \times 17}, 1070, 1071, \dots, 1104, 1105\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 17575; \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{705, 706, \dots, 743, 744, D_{19 \times 19}, 1106, 1107, \dots, 1144, 1145\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 19425; \\
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{661, 662, \dots, 703, 704, D_{21 \times 21}, 1146, 1147, \dots, 1188, 1189\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 21275; \\
 D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{613, 614, \dots, 659, 660, D_{23 \times 23}, 1190, 1191, \dots, 1236, 1237\}; & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 23125; \\
 D_{27 \times 27} &:= \{561, 562, \dots, 611, 612, D_{25 \times 25}, 1238, 1239, \dots, 1288, 1289\}; & S_{27 \times 27} &:= 24975; \\
 D_{29 \times 29} &:= \{505, 506, \dots, 559, 560, D_{27 \times 27}, 1290, 1291, \dots, 1344, 1345\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 26825; \\
 D_{31 \times 31} &:= \{445, 602, \dots, 503, 504, D_{29 \times 29}, 1346, 1347, \dots, 1404, 1405\}; & S_{31 \times 31} &:= 28675; \\
 D_{33 \times 33} &:= \{381, 382, \dots, 443, 444, D_{31 \times 31}, 1406, 1407, \dots, 1468, 1469\}; & S_{33 \times 33} &:= 30525; \\
 D_{35 \times 35} &:= \{313, 314, \dots, 299, 380, D_{33 \times 33}, 1470, 1471, \dots, 1536, 1537\}; & S_{35 \times 35} &:= 32375; \\
 D_{37 \times 37} &:= \{241, 242, \dots, 311, 312, D_{35 \times 35}, 1538, 1539, \dots, 1508, 1609\}; & S_{37 \times 37} &:= 34225; \\
 D_{39 \times 39} &:= \{165, 166, \dots, 239, 240, D_{37 \times 37}, 1610, 1611, \dots, 1684, 1685\}; & S_{39 \times 39} &:= 36075; \\
 D_{41 \times 41} &:= \{85, 86, \dots, 163, 164, D_{39 \times 39}, 1686, 1687, \dots, 1764, 1765\}; & S_{41 \times 41} &:= 37925; \\
 D_{43 \times 43} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 73, 84, D_{41 \times 41}, 1766, 1767, \dots, 1764, 1859\}; & S_{43 \times 43} &:= 39775.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 41. These are based on the magic squares of order 39 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.1 and 3.2.

2.2.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1521 by 165 to 1685 in Example 3.1 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{39 \times 39}$ appearing in Example 2.2, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 41 given by

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.2.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1521 by 81 to 1601 in Example 3.2 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{39 \times 39}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 41 given by

Blocks of order 13 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**

Result 2.2. *We have written a **block-bordered** magic square of order 43 in two different ways, where the **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 39, where each block of order 3 is a *semi-magic* square with *equal semi-magic sums*;
- (ii) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 39, where each block of order 13 is a *pandiagonal* magic square with *equal magic sums*.

2.3 Bordered Magic Squares of Order 46

Example 2.3. *Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 46 given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{1041, 1042, \dots, 1049, 1050, D_{4 \times 4}, 1067, 1068, \dots, 1075, 1076\}; & S_{6 \times 6} &:= 6351; \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{1027, 1028, \dots, 1039, 1040, D_{6 \times 6}, 1077, 1078, \dots, 1089, 1090\}; & S_{8 \times 8} &:= 8468; \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{1009, 1010, \dots, 1025, 1026, D_{8 \times 8}, 1091, 1092, \dots, 1087, 1108\}; & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 10585; \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{987, 988, \dots, 1007, 1008, D_{10 \times 10}, 1109, 1110, \dots, 1129, 1130\}; & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 12702; \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{961, 962, \dots, 985, 986, D_{12 \times 12}, 1131, 1145, \dots, 1155, 1156\}; & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 14819; \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{931, 932, \dots, 959, 960, D_{14 \times 14}, 1157, 1158, \dots, 1185, 1186\}; & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 16936; \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{897, 898, \dots, 929, 930, D_{16 \times 16}, 1187, 1188, \dots, 1219, 1220\}; & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 19053; \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{859, 860, \dots, 895, 896, D_{18 \times 18}, 1221, 1222, \dots, 1257, 1258\}; & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 21170; \\
 D_{22 \times 22} &:= \{817, 818, \dots, 857, 858, D_{20 \times 20}, 1259, 1260, \dots, 1299, 1300\}; & S_{22 \times 22} &:= 23287; \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{771, 772, \dots, 815, 816, D_{22 \times 22}, 1301, 1302, \dots, 1345, 1346\}; & S_{24 \times 24} &:= 25404; \\
 D_{26 \times 26} &:= \{721, 722, \dots, 769, 770, D_{24 \times 24}, 1347, 1348, \dots, 1391, 1396\}; & S_{26 \times 26} &:= 27521; \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{667, 668, \dots, 719, 720, D_{26 \times 26}, 1397, 1394, \dots, 1449, 1450\}; & S_{28 \times 28} &:= 29638; \\
 D_{30 \times 30} &:= \{609, 610, \dots, 665, 666, D_{28 \times 28}, 1451, 1452, \dots, 1485, 1508\}; & S_{30 \times 30} &:= 31775; \\
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{547, 548, \dots, 607, 608, D_{30 \times 30}, 1509, 1510, \dots, 1543, 1570\}; & S_{32 \times 32} &:= 33872; \\
 D_{34 \times 34} &:= \{481, 482, \dots, 545, 546, D_{32 \times 32}, 1571, 1572, \dots, 1635, 1636\}; & S_{34 \times 34} &:= 35989; \\
 D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{411, 412, \dots, 479, 480, D_{34 \times 34}, 1637, 1638, \dots, 1705, 1706\}; & S_{36 \times 36} &:= 38106; \\
 D_{38 \times 38} &:= \{337, 338, \dots, 409, 410, D_{36 \times 36}, 1707, 1708, \dots, 1779, 1780\}; & S_{38 \times 38} &:= 40223; \\
 D_{40 \times 40} &:= \{259, 260, \dots, 335, 336, D_{38 \times 38}, 1881, 1882, \dots, 1857, 1858\}; & S_{40 \times 40} &:= 42340; \\
 D_{42 \times 42} &:= \{177, 178, \dots, 257, 258, D_{40 \times 40}, 1859, 1860, \dots, 1939, 1940\}; & S_{42 \times 42} &:= 44457; \\
 D_{44 \times 44} &:= \{91, 92, \dots, 175, 176, D_{42 \times 42}, 1941, 1942, \dots, 2025, 2026\}; & S_{44 \times 44} &:= 46574; \\
 D_{46 \times 46} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 89, 90, D_{44 \times 44}, 2027, 2028, \dots, 2115, 2116\}; & S_{46 \times 46} &:= 48691.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are ten different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 46. These are based on the magic squares of orders 44, 42 and 40 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.11, 3.12, 3.7, 3.8, 3.9, 3.10, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6

2.3.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1936 by 91 to 2026 in Example 3.11 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{44 \times 44}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**.

2.3.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1936 by 91 to 2026 in Example 3.12 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{44 \times 44}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 11 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **different magic sums**.

2.3.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1764 by 177 to 1940 in Example 3.7 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{42 \times 42}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 3 are **magic squares** with **different magic sums**.

2.3.4 Forth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1764 by 177 to 1940 in Example 3.8 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{42 \times 42}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

A large table containing a 46x46 block-bordered magic square. The first 43 rows are labeled 2071 to 2094. The next 23 rows are labeled 2051 to 2073. The final row is labeled 45. The table contains numerical values in each cell, with colors alternating in a grid pattern (magenta, green, cyan, magenta).

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 with following sums:

$$S_{46 \times 46} := 48691, S_{44 \times 44} := 46574, S_{42 \times 42} := 44457 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 6351$$

Blocks of order 6 are **magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.3.5 Fifth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1764 by 177 to 1940 in Example 3.9 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{42 \times 42}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **different magic sums**.

2.3.6 Sixth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1764 by 177 to 1940 in Example 3.10 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{42 \times 42}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 14 are **magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.3.7 Seventh Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1600 by 259 to 1859 in Example 3.3 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{40 \times 40}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**.

2.3.8 Eighth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1600 by 259 to 1859 in Example 3.4 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{40 \times 40}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **different magic sums**.

2.3.9 Ninth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1600 by 259 to 1859 in Example 3.5 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{40 \times 40}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 8 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**. Moreover, blocks of order 8 are either **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** squares with different **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** sums resulting in **bimagic square** of order 40 with **bimagic sum** $S_{40 \times 40} := 53350220$.

2.3.10 Tenth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1600 by 259 to 1859 in Example 3.6 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{40 \times 40}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 46 given by

Blocks of order 10 are **magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

Result 2.3. *We have written a **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 in five different ways, where the **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 44, where each block of order 4 is a *pandiagonal* magic square with **equal magic sums**;
- (ii) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 44, where each block of order 11 is a *pandiagonal* magic square with **different magic sums**;
- (iii) *Magic square* of order 42, where each block of order 3 is a magic square with **different magic sums**;
- (iv) *Magic square* of order 42, where each block of order 6 is a magic square with **equal magic sums**;
- (v) *Magic square* of order 42, where each block of order 7 is a magic square with **different magic sums**;
- (vi) *Magic square* of order 42, where each block of order 14 is a magic square with **equal magic sums**;
- (vii) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 40, where each block of order 4 is a *pandiagonal* magic square with **equal magic sums**;
- (viii) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 40, where each block of order 5 is a *pandiagonal* magic square with **different magic sums**;
- (ix) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 40, where each block of order 8 is a *pandiagonal* magic square with **equal magic sums**. In this case, the magic square of order 40 is also a **bimagic square**, where each block of order 8 is either **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** with **different bimagic** and **semi-bimagic** sums;
- (x) *Magic square* of order 40, where each block of order 10 is a magic square with **equal magic sums**.

2.4 Bordered Magic Squares of Order 47

Example 2.4. *Let's consider a **bordered** magic square of order 47 given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{1101, 1102, 1103, 1104, 1105, 1106, 1107, 1108, 1109\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 3315; \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{1093, 1094, \dots, 1099, 1100, D_{3 \times 3}, 1110, 1111, \dots, 1116, 1117\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 5525; \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{1081, 1082, \dots, 1091, 1092, D_{5 \times 5}, 1118, 1119, \dots, 1128, 1129\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 7735; \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{1065, 1066, \dots, 1079, 1080, D_{7 \times 7}, 1130, 1131, \dots, 1144, 1145\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 9945; \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{1045, 1046, \dots, 1063, 1064, D_{9 \times 9}, 1146, 1147, \dots, 1164, 1165\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 12155; \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{1021, 1022, \dots, 1043, 1044, D_{11 \times 11}, 1166, 1167, \dots, 1188, 1189\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 14365; \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{993, 994, \dots, 1019, 1020, D_{13 \times 13}, 1190, 1191, \dots, 1216, 1217\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 16575; \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{961, 962, \dots, 991, 992, D_{15 \times 15}, 1218, 1219, \dots, 1248, 1249\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 18785; \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{925, 926, \dots, 959, 960, D_{17 \times 17}, 1250, 1251, \dots, 1284, 1285\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 20995; \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{885, 886, \dots, 923, 924, D_{19 \times 19}, 1286, 1287, \dots, 1324, 1325\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 23205; \\
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{841, 842, \dots, 883, 884, D_{21 \times 21}, 1326, 1327, \dots, 1368, 1369\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 25415; \\
 D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{793, 794, \dots, 839, 840, D_{23 \times 23}, 1370, 1371, \dots, 1416, 1417\}; & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 27625; \\
 D_{27 \times 27} &:= \{741, 742, \dots, 791, 792, D_{25 \times 25}, 1418, 1419, \dots, 1468, 1469\}; & S_{27 \times 27} &:= 29835; \\
 D_{29 \times 29} &:= \{685, 686, \dots, 739, 740, D_{27 \times 27}, 1470, 1471, \dots, 1524, 1525\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 32045; \\
 D_{31 \times 31} &:= \{625, 782, \dots, 683, 684, D_{29 \times 29}, 1526, 1527, \dots, 1584, 1585\}; & S_{31 \times 31} &:= 34255; \\
 D_{33 \times 33} &:= \{561, 562, \dots, 623, 624, D_{31 \times 31}, 1586, 1587, \dots, 1648, 1649\}; & S_{33 \times 33} &:= 36465; \\
 D_{35 \times 35} &:= \{493, 494, \dots, 479, 560, D_{33 \times 33}, 1650, 1651, \dots, 1716, 1717\}; & S_{35 \times 35} &:= 38675; \\
 D_{37 \times 37} &:= \{421, 422, \dots, 491, 492, D_{35 \times 35}, 1718, 1719, \dots, 1688, 1789\}; & S_{37 \times 37} &:= 40885; \\
 D_{39 \times 39} &:= \{345, 346, \dots, 419, 420, D_{37 \times 37}, 1790, 1791, \dots, 1864, 1865\}; & S_{39 \times 39} &:= 43095; \\
 D_{41 \times 41} &:= \{265, 266, \dots, 343, 344, D_{39 \times 39}, 1866, 1867, \dots, 1944, 1945\}; & S_{41 \times 41} &:= 45305; \\
 D_{43 \times 43} &:= \{181, 182, \dots, 263, 264, D_{41 \times 41}, 1946, 1947, \dots, 1944, 2029\}; & S_{43 \times 43} &:= 47515; \\
 D_{45 \times 45} &:= \{93, 94, \dots, 179, 180, D_{43 \times 43}, 2030, 2031, \dots, 2116, 2117\}; & S_{45 \times 45} &:= 49725; \\
 D_{47 \times 47} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 91, 92, D_{45 \times 45}, 2118, 2119, \dots, 2208, 2209\}; & S_{47 \times 47} &:= 51935.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are four different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 47. These are based on the magic squares of order 45 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.13, 3.14, 3.15, 3.16 and 3.17.

2.4.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2025 by 93 to 2117 in Example 3.13 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{45 \times 45}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 given by

$$S_{47 \times 47} := 51935, S_{45 \times 45} := 49725 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 3315.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.4.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2025 by 93 to 2117 in Example 3.14 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{45 \times 45}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 given by

$$S_{47 \times 47} := 51935, S_{45 \times 45} := 49725 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 5525.$$

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**.

2.4.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2025 by 93 to 2117 in Example 3.16 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{45 \times 45}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 given by

$$S_{47 \times 47} := 51935 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{45 \times 45} := 49725$$

Blocks of order 9 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **different magic sums**. In this case the blocks of order 3 are semi-magic sums. In each block of order 9, the order 3 blocks are of equal semi-magic sums.

2.4.4 Forth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2025 by 93 to 2117 in Example 3.16 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{45 \times 45}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 given by

$$S_{47 \times 47} := 51935, S_{45 \times 45} := 49725 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 9945.$$

Blocks of order 9 are **magic squares** with **equal magic sums**. In this case, we don't have any property of block of order 3.

2.4.5 Fifth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2025 by 93 to 2117 in Example 3.17 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{45 \times 45}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 given by

$$S_{47 \times 47} := 51935, \quad \text{and} \quad S_{45 \times 45} := 49725.$$

Blocks of order 15 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **different magic sums**. Moreover, in each block of order 15, the blocks of order 3 are of equal magic sums.

2.4.6 Sixth Way

In this case the **block-bordered** magic square given in **Second Way** also works for the **pandiagonal** magic square for the blocks of order 15.

Result 2.4. *We have written a **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 in five different ways, where the **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square with equal semi-magic sums**;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where each block of order 5 is a **pandiagonal magic square with equal magic sums**;*
- (iii) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where each block of order 9 is a **pandiagonal magic square with different magic sums**;*
- (iv) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where each block of order 9 is a **magic square with equal magic sums**;*
- (v) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where each block of order 15 is a **pandiagonal magic square with different magic sums**;*
- (vi) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where each block of order 15 is a **pandiagonal magic square with equal magic sums**.*

2.5 Bordered Magic Squares of Order 53

Example 2.5. *Let's consider a **bordered magic square** of order 53 given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{1401, 1402, 1403, 1404, 1405, 1406, 1407, 1408, 1409\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 4215; \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{1393, 1394, \dots, 1399, 1400, D_{3 \times 3}, 1410, 1411, \dots, 1416, 1417\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 7025; \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{1381, 1382, \dots, 1391, 1392, D_{5 \times 5}, 1418, 1419, \dots, 1428, 1429\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 9835; \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{1365, 1366, \dots, 1379, 1380, D_{7 \times 7}, 1430, 1431, \dots, 1444, 1445\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 12645; \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{1345, 1346, \dots, 1363, 1364, D_{9 \times 9}, 1446, 1447, \dots, 1464, 1465\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 15455; \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{1321, 1322, \dots, 1343, 1344, D_{11 \times 11}, 1466, 1467, \dots, 1488, 1489\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 18265; \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{1293, 1294, \dots, 1319, 1320, D_{13 \times 13}, 1490, 1491, \dots, 1516, 1517\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 21075; \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{1261, 1262, \dots, 1291, 1292, D_{15 \times 15}, 1518, 1519, \dots, 1548, 1549\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 23885; \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{1225, 1226, \dots, 1259, 1260, D_{17 \times 17}, 1550, 1551, \dots, 1584, 1585\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 25451; \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{1185, 1186, \dots, 1223, 1224, D_{19 \times 19}, 1586, 1587, \dots, 1624, 1625\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 29505; \\
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{1141, 1142, \dots, 1183, 1184, D_{21 \times 21}, 1626, 1627, \dots, 1668, 1669\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 32315; \\
 D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{1093, 1094, \dots, 1139, 1140, D_{23 \times 23}, 1670, 1671, \dots, 1716, 1717\}; & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 34007; \\
 D_{27 \times 27} &:= \{1041, 1042, \dots, 1091, 1092, D_{25 \times 25}, 1718, 1719, \dots, 1768, 1769\}; & S_{27 \times 27} &:= 37935; \\
 D_{29 \times 29} &:= \{985, 986, \dots, 1039, 1040, D_{27 \times 27}, 1770, 1771, \dots, 1824, 1825\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 40745; \\
 D_{31 \times 31} &:= \{925, 1082, \dots, 983, 984, D_{29 \times 29}, 1826, 1827, \dots, 1884, 1885\}; & S_{31 \times 31} &:= 43555; \\
 D_{33 \times 33} &:= \{861, 862, \dots, 923, 924, D_{31 \times 31}, 1886, 1887, \dots, 1948, 1949\}; & S_{33 \times 33} &:= 46365; \\
 D_{35 \times 35} &:= \{793, 794, \dots, 779, 860, D_{33 \times 33}, 1950, 1951, \dots, 2016, 2017\}; & S_{35 \times 35} &:= 49175; \\
 D_{37 \times 37} &:= \{721, 722, \dots, 791, 792, D_{35 \times 35}, 2018, 2019, \dots, 1988, 2089\}; & S_{37 \times 37} &:= 51985; \\
 D_{39 \times 39} &:= \{645, 646, \dots, 719, 720, D_{37 \times 37}, 2090, 2091, \dots, 2164, 2165\}; & S_{39 \times 39} &:= 54795; \\
 D_{41 \times 41} &:= \{565, 566, \dots, 643, 644, D_{39 \times 39}, 2166, 2167, \dots, 2244, 2245\}; & S_{41 \times 41} &:= 57605; \\
 D_{43 \times 43} &:= \{481, 482, \dots, 563, 564, D_{41 \times 41}, 2246, 2247, \dots, 2244, 2329\}; & S_{43 \times 43} &:= 60415; \\
 D_{45 \times 45} &:= \{393, 394, \dots, 479, 480, D_{43 \times 43}, 2330, 2331, \dots, 2416, 2417\}; & S_{45 \times 45} &:= 63225; \\
 D_{47 \times 47} &:= \{301, 302, \dots, 391, 392, D_{45 \times 45}, 2418, 2419, \dots, 2508, 2509\}; & S_{47 \times 47} &:= 66035; \\
 D_{49 \times 49} &:= \{205, 206, \dots, 299, 300, D_{47 \times 47}, 2510, 2511, \dots, 2604, 2605\}; & S_{49 \times 49} &:= 68845; \\
 D_{51 \times 51} &:= \{105, 105, \dots, 203, 204, D_{49 \times 49}, 2606, 2607, \dots, 2704, 2705\}; & S_{51 \times 51} &:= 71655; \\
 D_{53 \times 53} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 103, 104, D_{51 \times 51}, 2706, 2707, \dots, 2808, 2809\}; & S_{53 \times 53} &:= 74465.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are three different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 53. These are based on the magic squares of order 51 and 49 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.19, 3.20 and 3.18.

2.5.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2601 by 105 to 2705 in Example 3.19 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{51 \times 51}$ appearing in Example 2.5, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 53 given by

following sums:

$$S_{53 \times 53} := 74465, S_{51 \times 51} := 71655 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 4215.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.5.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2601 by 105 to 2705 in Example 3.20 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{51 \times 51}$ appearing in Example 2.5, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 53 given by

following sums:

$$S_{53 \times 53} := 74465, S_{51 \times 51} := 71655 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{17 \times 17} := 23885.$$

Blocks of order 17 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**.

2.5.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 2401 by 205 to 2605 in Example 3.18 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{51 \times 51}$ appearing in Example 2.5, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 53 given by

following sums:

$$S_{53 \times 53} := 74465, S_{51 \times 51} := 71655, S_{49 \times 49} := 68845 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{7 \times 7} := 9835.$$

Blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **equal magic sums**. Moreover, the magic square of order 49 is **bimagic** with **bimagic sum**, $Sb_{49 \times 49} := 120266825$.

Result 2.5. *We have written a **block-bordered** magic square of order 53 in three different ways, where the **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 51, where each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square with equal semi-magic sums**;
- (ii) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 51, where each block of order 17 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with **equal magic sums**;
- (iii) *Pandiagonal* magic square of order 49, where each block of order 7 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with **equal magic sums**.
Moreover, in this the magic square of order 49 is **bimagic**.

3 Appendix: Block-Wise Magic Squares

3.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of order 39

3.1.1 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.1. *A magic square of order 39 formed by 169 blocks of order 3 is given by*

Thus, we have a magic square of order 42, where each block of order 14 is a magic square with **equal magic sums**.

3.4 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 44

3.4.1 Blocks of Order 4

Example 3.11. *A magic square of order 44 formed by 121 blocks of magic squares of order 4 is given by*

Thus, we have a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 44, where each block of order 11 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with **different magic sums**.

3.5 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 45

3.5.1 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.13. *A magic square of order 45 formed by 225 blocks of magic squares of order 3 is given by*

semi-magic sums.

3.5.2 Blocks of Order 5

Example 3.14. *A magic square of order 45 formed by 81 blocks of magic squares of order 5 is given by*

Thus, the magic square of order 45 is **pandiagonal**, where each block of order 9 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with **different magic sums**.

3.5.4 Blocks of Order 9: Second Way

Example 3.16. *A magic square of order 45 formed by 25 blocks of magic squares of order 9 is given by*

Thus, the magic square of order 45 is with **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 15. The magic squares of order 15 are with **different magic sums**.

3.5.6 Blocks of Order 15: Second Way

The example given above in subsection 3.6.1 for the blocks of order 5 also works for the blocks of order 15. In this case, we have **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 15 with equal magic sums.

3.6 Block-Wise Bimagic Square of Order 49

3.6.1 Blocks of Order 7

Example 3.18. *A bimagic square of order 49 formed by 49 blocks of magic squares of order 7 is given by*

Remark 3.1. Summarizing all the three papers [54, 55] and this one, we have constructed **block-bordered** magic squares of orders 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 19, 22, 23, 26, 29, 31, 34, 37, 38, 41, 43, 46, 47 and 53. The **prime order magic squares** are 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47 and 53. The **double prime orders** are 10 (2×5), 14 (2×7), 22 (2×11), 26 (2×13), 34 (2×17), 38 (2×19) and 46 (2×23). In order to construct these magic squares we used **block-wise** magic squares of orders 12, 15, 18, 20, 21, 24, 25, 27, 28, 30, 32, 36, 39, 40, 42, 44, 45, 49 and 51. Except 25 and 49, there are always multiple choices considered for the **block-bordered** magic squares. Resulting in total 54 **block-bordered** magic squares for the 19 bordered magic squares. The work on **block-wise** magic squares up to order 45 is done by author in [35, ?]. The block-wise magic squares of orders 49 and 51 are considered directly, without details. Details of these along with magic square of orders 48 and 50 shall be given in another work. The magic square of order 51 with blocks of order 17 is considered directly from the software by H. White [11].

4 Author's Contributions to Magic Squares

The **item-wise** author's work on magic squares is as follows:

1. **Digital Numbers Magic Squares** - [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 46];
2. **Connections with Genetic Tables and Shannon's entropy** - [21];
3. **Selfie and Palindromic-type Magic Squares** - [22, 37, 46];
4. **Intervally Distributed and Block-Wise Magic Squares** - [23, 24, 25, 37];
5. **Multi-digits and Number Patterns Magic Squares** - [26, 36];
6. **Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares with Uniformity, Minimum Sum and Pythagorean Triples** - [27, 28];
7. **Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares** - [20, 29, 30, 31, 32, 35, 38, 40];
8. **Magic Crosses: Repeated and Non Repeated Entries** - [33];
9. **Representations of Letters and Numbers With Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 6** - [34];
10. **Bordered Magic Squares** - [41, 42, 43, 44, 45];
11. **Block-Bordered Magic Squares** - [54, 55];
12. **2-Digits Magic and Bimagic Squares** - [46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53].

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